
Motivation in English Language Learning: A Study on Preparatory School Students at Universities

Cem Yağmur Genç,
cemyenc@gmail.com

Paper Received on 14-11-2023, Accepted on 12-12-2023,
Published on 14-12-23; DOI: 10.36993/ RJOE.2023.8.4.194

Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the role of motivation in English language learning, taking into consideration age groups and genders, and shed light on their effects. Additionally, this study attempted to determine whether the type of high school they attended and the current university they were enrolled in (public or private) had influence on students' internal and external motivation. The study was conducted at foundation and public universities in Ankara, with a total of 212 student participants. Among the participants, 108 were studying at private universities, and 104 were studying at public universities' preparatory schools. The students were at least at the pre-Intermediate level in the preparatory schools of their universities. The participants' ages ranged from 18-40, with an average age of 29, and there were 103 males and 108 females. Language Learning Orientations Scale (Noels et al. 2003) was used to measure students' motivation type. The Social Sciences Statistics Program was used for result analysis, and the validity was assessed through Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient (Cronbach, 1951). The results indicated no significant difference between genders and age groups, while differences were observed based on the type of high school they graduated and university they were currently studying at.

Keywords: Intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, lack of motivation, second language learning motivation, foreign language learning motivation.

Introduction

Any effective activity may be traced back to the motivation and effort of the individuals involved. When these two elements are taken into account, motivation may be seen as the first stage in piquing an interest and turning it into a choice to engage in an activity, with effort perhaps entering the process later on. Williams and Burden (1997) defined motivation as the formation of feelings and information that prompts an effortful, conscious action. On the other hand, motivation is present at every phase of a fruitful endeavor, contingent upon the exertion. Gardner (1985) suggests that a combination of other human factors and motivation—personal desire and effort—can lead to the achievement of the objective. Without any internal or personal motivation, a person may aspire to something like success because they are intrigued, engaged, or content. Extrinsic variables like money, pressure, rewards, and interpersonal interactions might be enough to encourage learners.

There are several variables that might impact language acquisition when teaching and learning a language is taken into account. Several variables contribute to language

acquisition, such as inadequate linguistic input from the environment, insufficient opportunities for interacting with native speakers, and a dearth of supportive role models. Since the concept was first put forth by Gardner and Lambert (1959), a great deal of educators and scholars have claimed that, in reaction to these unfavorable circumstances, the concept of motivation has been essential to determining whether or not students studying English as a Second Language (ESL) and English as a Foreign Language (EFL) succeed. Stated differently, motivation may serve as both an initial incentive to study and a significant tool during the challenging process of learning a foreign language (Cheng & Dörnyei, 2007). This is supported by Cheng and Dörnyei's study. Dörnyei (1998) asserts that motivation is the primary catalyst that ignites the desire to acquire a second language. Motivation eventually drives the desire to continue the challenging and sometimes time-consuming acquisition process in the same direction; in fact, motivation is the presumption behind all other incentives associated with L2 learning.

Several academics and researchers "who have dedicated their professional lives to the investigation of second language acquisition" (Aljumah, 2020) have conducted a significant quantity of study emphasizing motivation's importance. The most significant component missing from the language learning process, according to Tremblay and Gardner's (1995) research, is motivation. Consequently, the notion of motivation has consistently been central to a wide range of theories about the learning of foreign languages (Rajab, et al., 2012).

When adverse effects of unfavourable conditions are taken into account, motivation

and its types should not be ignored in language learning and its achievement. The central aim of this study is to have a better insight about the role of motivation and the types of motivation for the students towards language learning. In addition to this, the researcher has a purpose to examine what type of motivation -intrinsic or extrinsic-affects largely and more importantly students' language learning process in general and English in particular, to evaluate whether the students have one, both or none of the motivation types.

Research Questions

1. Is there any significant difference between self-determination motivation types of students studying English at public and foundation universities?
2. Is there any significant difference between the types of self-determination motivation with respect to the type of high school students graduated from?
3. Is there a relationship between the motivational structure of English learners and their age?
4. Does the motivational structure of English learners differ with respect their gender?

Motivation

Motivation, in the words of Harmer (2001), is the inner desire that propels a person to finish tasks and reach an objective. To elaborate on the description, Williams & Burden (1997) say that motivation is a kind of cognitive process that triggers an action-oriented decision-making mechanism, leading to sustained ideation and physical exertion in order to achieve a goal. It can be

seen as the mental and physical spark that propels someone to start or finish a task they are passionate about.

Reeve (1997) asserts that motivation theory is essential because it enables us to understand the cause and direction of an individual's drive. Behavior that is comparatively intense, profound, and persistent is referred to as drive. The word "direction" describes actions that are intended to accomplish a particular objective. This same motivation gives kids a purpose, which concentrates their attention and guides their behavior toward particular objectives. Additionally, Reeve (1997:11) included the following:

- Motivation comprises both aptitude and abstention dispositions.
- Motivation has distinctions in terms of density and kind.
- Motivation can be self-regulated or environmentally regulated.
- Motivation is something about desire and will.
- Motivation is a dynamic process.
- Motive incentives may change in time and place.
- Motives have been arranged hierarchically.
- We might not be really aware of the basis of our behaviors for motivation.
- Motivational tenet may show difference.

According to Rowel and Ensook (2009), motivation may be characterized as a psychological continuum resulting from the interaction between the environment and the individual, thereby fulfilling a key mission for learning and progress. According to

Pintrich (2003), this process occurs as a result of people's decisions and behaviors, which are impacted by cultural and societal variables as well as fundamental necessities. These decisions, the dread of these decisions and their repercussions, the devotion and involvement of persons to the behaviors all emerge from psychological needs (Locke & Latham, 2013).

According to Locke (2002), people obtain the spark and desire to reach a goal, and they act appropriately as a consequence of the primary source of urge-motivation, which acts as specified cognitive and organismic processes determining how they behave. Motivation reflects its aspect, depth, and continuance period by functioning as the actuator of these behaviors (Pintrich & DeGroot, 1990). Simply expressed, motivation is the driving force behind an individual's behaviors toward a certain objective (Hidi & Harackiewicz, 2000).

Singh (2011) defines motivation as "the determination that drives people to pursue their goals despite significant obstacles." Furthermore, Ayub (2010) defines motivation as a multifaceted notion that includes a desire to act as well as being interested, having a learning-oriented point of view, being active, and successful. As a consequence, motivation may be described as a combination of positive behaviors and feelings when task performance is taken into account. Motivation, according to Zlate and Cucui (2015), may be defined as an internal state that regulates how an individual acts in order to attain a given goal. Furthermore, motivation may be a big aspect that affects people's life (Hubackova, 2014).

Intrinsic, Extrinsic Motivation and Amotivation

According to Harmer (2001), everyone might be driven by the pleasure of learning new things or the desire to feel a lot better. Intrinsic motivation, according to Deci and Ryan (1985), is an inherent inclination that occurs from birth to allow interest and capacity to explore and solve obstacles. They also say that this form of motivation is based on natural sentiments and wants that people had when they needed competence. Deci (in Brown, 2001) also emphasizes that intrinsically motivated activities do not have explicit rewards. According to Filimonov (2017), furthermore, people may feel driven when the work or activity is essential to them, demonstrating that they have intrinsic motivation. Furthermore, Noels et al. (1999) describe intrinsic motivation as engaging in an action that the individual performing it finds delightful and rewarding. It shows up as psychological urges, personal interests, and endeavors to grow. The idea, according to these researchers, is all about having the flexibility to pick an activity to participate in, which might provide a challenge to which individuals can rise. Furthermore, intrinsic motivation provides people with a natural degree of drive that increases learning without the need of rewards or pressures (Deci et al. 1991). Interest, for example, might spark a desire to engage in an activity in the absence of these incentives and demands.

Needs fuel and guide our activity, and they encourage us to seek out circumstances in which we feel we will be involved and satisfied (Deci & Ryan, 2000). They also believe that learners' needs may be inactive or mute. As a result, learners may not always be

active and may be hesitant to participate in their surroundings. Schools may confront the same problem; professors may encounter reluctant students who refuse to engage in class, and this scenario might shatter a student's bravery. In other words, learners may not always be effective in igniting their motivation. They may look for something encouraging in their surroundings. Teachers at schools, according to Reeve (1997), display a range of activities that might be characterized as external drives, often known as extrinsic motivation. According to Noels et al. (1999), extrinsic motivation behaviors, unlike intrinsic motivation behaviors, may be put into practice to achieve something objective.

According to Kowal and Fortier (1997), people learning a language or doing another work may have extrinsic motivation if they are provided a reward, threatened with penalty, or receive admiration or acceptance from others for their activities. Furthermore, Cherry (2016) states that even if there is no initial desire or motivation, extrinsic motivations can impact the stimulation of will and engagement. For example, if a worker is awarded for a good performance, which is an example of extrinsic motivation, he or she would know that his or her work is valued.

Extrinsically driven people engage in tasks for a reward. The authors argue that "When individuals are extrinsically motivated, they hold some desired outcome as a goal (e.g., getting a good grade or avoiding punishment), they recognize that a certain way of behaving is an expedient means to that goal, and they make plans to modify their behaviour in such a manner that they are likely to experience the desired

outcome." Internal motives, according to numerous academics, are more potent than external motivations. Nonetheless, according to Cherry (2016), some researches obtain some fundamental findings concerning the efficacy of external drives over internal drives.

- External incentives help improve internal drives
- Appreciation is able to enhance intrinsic motivation
- Intrinsic motivation may diminish if external incentives are presented for insignificant performances or behaviors.

Amotivation, the third component of SDT, may signify that people have little or no desire to accomplish activities. In other words, people have the option of doing nothing or performing inactively. Many research, like Legault, Green-Demers, and Pelletier (2006), reveal that people suffer with amotivation, especially in school. According to Rotter (1966) and Seligman (1975), this may be due to feelings that people lack the ability to attain their goals. Furthermore, Bandura (1977) and Deci (1975) argue that this may be attributable to a perceived lack of expertise. Finally, Ryan (1995) claims that it might result from people's activities or consequences being useles.

Amotivation is defined by Noels et al. (2000) as the idea that there is no link between one's performance and one's outcomes. People feel that the consequences are the product of others, therefore they tend to cease or finish the action with no intrinsic or extrinsic drive, according to their definition. The concept of other factors determining their actions and consequences,

according to Janosz, Le Blanc, Boulerice, and Tremblay (2000), leads to indifference to willed aims. Individuals who are uninspired get disappointed and unhappy as a result of these sentiments and moods, reducing their ingenuity and production, according to Legault et al. (2006). These scholars also suggest that a lack of belief in oneself and one's talents can produce amotivation, which they credit as the major cause of their amotivation. Their second assertion is that amotivation is connected to people's fear of not being able to exert enough effort to attain their objective, resulting in academic failure. Furthermore, Deci and Ryan (1985a) suggest that a person may feel amotivation if he or she considers the work and herself/himself are irrelevant. According to Murdock (1999), any unfavorable sentiments about the surroundings, such as school or job, might induce a sense of amotivation. Finally, Legault et al. (2006) claim that if people do not experience pleasure while performing a task, they may experience amotivation.

Previous Studies about Motivation in Language Learning

Researchers have diverse perspectives on many sorts of motivation. According to Lucas (2010), learners are intrinsically driven to improve their speaking and reading skills, as well as their knowledge and success. Tercanlioglu (2001) claims that Turkish learners have positive attitudes toward reading because they read for both intrinsic and extrinsic reasons.

according to Dital (2012), learners were highly motivated and had favorable attitudes regarding learning English. They were driven both instrumentally and integratively. Chang (2010) noted that the class group increased learners' motivation and

that enthusiastic peers made them feel more at ease. Another result was that the kids who were not paying attention demotivated their classmates. According to Moskovsy and Alrabai (2009), instrumental motivation is more important than integrative motivation in EFL learning. This study also discovered that integrative motivation is more significant to ESL learning.

According to Moivavaziri (2009), language learners were driven both instrumentally and integratively. Students were discovered to be particularly motivated to study English. According to Al-Otaibi (2004), motivated learners commit a large amount of effort to attaining their goals in learning a foreign language, and motivated learners acquire language more successfully than uninspired learners. According to Al-Hazemi (2000), learners who have a strong desire to study a language can obtain a high level of proficiency in the target language.

According to MacIntyre (1999), a secure classroom environment is critical for motivation, and learners feel at ease studying a language in this setting. According to Good and Brophy (1994), motivation cannot be developed in a demanding classroom, and teachers must create an effective learning environment for their pupils. They went on to suggest that language acquisition is most effective in a calm and inviting setting.

According to Ziahosseini and Salehi (2008), extrinsic motivation has minimal influence on the choice of language learning approaches. They emphasized the intrinsic motivation of Iranian EFL students. Sadighi and Maghsudi (2000) evaluated the impact of integrative and instrumental motivation on the English proficiency of EFL learners in Iran. This study's findings demonstrated a

significant difference in the means of English proficiency scores of integratively driven learners versus instrumentally motivated learners.

Methodology Research Design

This study adopted a quantitative method research design by using quantitative data collection method, a survey, in order to validate and display strong and reliable results about the language learning motivation of the sample. There is one phase in this study and the questionnaire was adapted 4-point scale to obtain more reliable results, which the original one is 7-point scale. It includes a language learning motivation questionnaire of Noels et al. (2003) "Language Learning Orientations Scale – Intrinsic Motivation, Extrinsic Motivation, and Amotivation Subscales (LLOS-IEA)" comprising 21 statements about language learning motivation. The sample group will choose their motivation level via this 4-point Likert scale.

Population and Sample

The participants in this study are being planned as 108 students studying at foundation and 104 students at state universities: 212 pupils in total. The participants' level of proficiency will be at least at pre-intermediate level of English according to an international standard to describe language ability, which is the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). The participants were chosen intentionally according to their level as the questionnaire was given in English and it was expected from the students to understand and choose the statements correctly.

Data Collection Instruments

In the proposed study, one main instrument was implemented namely, a questionnaire. It includes a language learning motivation questionnaire of Noels et al. (2003) – ‘‘Language Learning Orientations Scale – Intrinsic Motivation, Extrinsic Motivation, and Amotivation Subscales (LLOS-IEA)’’ - comprising 21 statements about language learning motivation.

In the phase of the study, there are several reasons to choose a questionnaire to gather data for the study. The first main reason is that the study’s design necessitated the use of a questionnaire. Besides, the practicality of the questionnaires cannot be ignored, which means it was easy to conduct and score. Lastly, conducting the questionnaire is time saving not only for the researcher but also for the participants while making the participants feel safe in their own environment to answer the questions in a correct way.

The questionnaire of Noels et al. (2003) – ‘‘Language Learning Orientations Scale – Intrinsic Motivation, Extrinsic Motivation, and Amotivation Subscales (LLOS-IEA)’’ which was originally adapted from Academic Motivation Scale of Vallerand et al. (1992) was used for the research. The questionnaire consists of three main parts; amotivation that has 3 statements, intrinsic motivation (IM) that has three distinct parts with 9 statements; knowledge, accomplishment and stimulation, and extrinsic motivation (EM) that has 3 three different parts with 9 statements; external regulation, introjected regulation and identified regulation. The students choose their motivation level by rating the statements in 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ‘‘Absolutely inappropriate’’ to 4 ‘‘Absolutely

appropriate’’. Items which are used in the questionnaire of Noels et al. (2003) were taken and adapted from the questionnaire of Vallerand et al. (1992), The Academic Motivation Scale. The scale’s main categories are based on the SDT (Self Determination Theory).

Even though the number of scales is numerous, the questionnaire used in the study has a lot of advantages. The first main positive side is the language level of it is not high and B1 level of the language is enough to grasp and do the questionnaire. Secondly, amotivation is also taken into consideration along with other types of motivation. The questionnaire has been used in many studies and proved the reliability and validity level.

Data Collection Procedures

The researcher applied and took permission from the administration of preparatory schools of the universities which are state and foundation to conduct the study. The participants were explained that they did not have to do the questionnaire and it was volunteer based to be collected a reliable data, which they were also informed that their names should not be written, and all the information and data would be kept confidential and would not affect their grades. The expected number of the data collection was 500 participants, yet 212 participants volunteered the study. The reason for not reaching the targeted number in data collection was due to the implementation of blended distance learning in universities that emerged after the earthquakes in Turkey. The questionnaire was conducted in participants own classes and took about 10-15 minutes.

Data Analysis

For the demographic variables,

descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, percent, etc.) were performed. Before starting the analysis of the data in the study, it was examined whether the dependent variable of self-determination motivation types showed a normal distribution or not, by considering the ± 2 value of kurtosis and skewness values (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). In case of normal distribution, independent sample t-test and Pearson product correlation coefficient parametric analyses were used to answer the research questions. In the absence of a normal distribution, non-parametric equivalents of parametric tests, Mann-Whitney U and Spearman rho analyses were used (Field, 2017). In the independent sample t-test or Mann-Whitney U tests, there should be one continuous variable and one independent variable with at most two subcategories. As a result of the analysis, it was checked whether

the mean scores of the dependent variable differ significantly among the subcategories of the independent variable. Pearson products correlation coefficient or Spearman rho correlation analysis was converted into a correlation coefficient between two continuous or at most two subcategory variables, the value of ± 1 . With this coefficient, both the severity and direction of the relationship between the two variables were able to be determined. Relationship analysis was not used in making cause-effect inference (Büyüköztürk, 2018; Çokluk et al., 2018; Field, 2017).

Normal distribution

Before starting the analysis of the data, the normal distribution of the dependent variables of self-determination motivation types used in the research was examined and the kurtosis and skewness values were given in the table below.

Table 1. Normal Distribution

The dependent variable		Kurtosis	Skewness
Motivation	Lack of motivation	1.585	1.492
Extrinsic Motivation – External Regulation	External regulation extrinsic motivation	-.829	.167
Extrinsic Motivation - Introjected Regulation	Introjected regulation extrinsic motivation	.041	1.136
Extrinsic Motivation - Identified Regulation	Identified regulation extrinsic motivation	-.081	-.255
Intrinsic Motivation - Knowledge	Intrinsic motivation to know	-.892	.251
Intrinsic Motivation - Accomplishment	Intrinsic motivation to succeed	-.815	-.013
Intrinsic Motivation - Stimulation	Intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation	-.763	-.421

When the dependent variables examined in the study were examined, it was observed that the kurtosis and skewness values remained within ± 2.00 . According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), the values of kurtosis and skewness must be between ± 2.00 for a data to be considered as having a normal distribution. In this case, it is assumed that the dependent variables of the study are normally distributed.

Results

In this section, the research findings are given below in order around the research questions.

Is there any significant difference between the self-determination motivation types of students studying English at public and foundation universities?

In order to answer this research question, each sub-dimension of the self-determination motivation scale was analysed with the independent sample t-test, taking into account the status of education in public or foundation universities. The descriptive statistics of each motivation sub-dimension of the students according to their state or foundation university education are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of university students' motivation sub-dimensions by type of university and independent sample t-test results

	University type	Average	Standard deviation	Standard error	t(210)
Lack of motivation	State	4.36	2.437	.240	-2.219*
	Foundation	5.16	2.786	.267	
External regulation extrinsic motivation	State	9.36	2.279	.225	-.142
	Foundation	9.40	2.290	.219	
Introjected regulation extrinsic motivation	State	7.24	2.932	.289	-.367
	Foundation	7.39	3.088	.296	
Identified regulation extrinsic motivation	State	10.14	2.397	.236	4.255**
	Foundation	8.67	2.607	.250	
Intrinsic motivation to know	State	9.51	2.453	.242	.931
	Foundation	9.19	2.573	.246	
Intrinsic motivation to succeed	State	9.50	2.619	.258	1.210
	Foundation	9.07	2.570	.246	
Intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation	State	9.27	2.730	.269	.800
	Foundation	8.96	2.880	.276	
Note. State university n = 103, foundation university n = 109					
* p < .05, ** p < .01					

When the results in Table 6 are examined, significant differences are observed in the motivation sub-dimensions of the type of university the students attended, $t(210) = -2,219$, $p < ,05$, and identified regulation, $t(210) = 4,255$, $p < ,01$. The amotivation scores of the students studying at foundation universities were higher than the students studying at public universities. On the subject of the identified regulation sub-dimension, the scores of the students studying at the state university were higher than the students studying at the foundation university. As a result, it can be said that studying at a state university reduces the learners' amotivation and at the same time increases their identification motivation.

Is there any significant difference between the types of self-determination motivation with respect to the type of high school students graduated from?

In order to answer this research question, each sub-dimension of the self-determination motivation scale were analysed with an independent sample t-test, taking into account the state or foundation universities. The descriptive statistics and independent sample t-test results of each motivation sub-dimension of the students according to the students' high school graduation from foundation or public schools are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of university students' motivation sub-dimensions according to the type of high school they graduated from and independent sample t-test results

	Type of high school graduated	Average	Standard deviation	Standard error	t(210)
Lack of motivation	State	4.52	2.422	.237	-1.350
	Foundation	5.01	2.837	.273	
External regulation extrinsic motivation	State	9.50	2.194	.215	.738
	Foundation	9.27	2.363	.227	
Introjected regulation extrinsic motivation	State	7.21	2.831	.278	-.518
	Foundation	7.43	3.178	.306	
Identified regulation extrinsic motivation	State	10.05	2.291	.225	3.762**
	Foundation	8.74	2.739	.264	
Intrinsic motivation to know	State	9.47	2.327	.228	.693
	Foundation	9.23	2.688	.259	
Intrinsic motivation to succeed	State	9.39	2.439	.239	.611
	Foundation	9.18	2.747	.264	
Intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation	State	9.34	2.587	.254	1.138
	Foundation	8.90	2.998	.289	
Note. State university n = 104, foundation university n = 108					
* p < ,05, ** p < .01					

When Table 7 is examined, the type of high school students graduated from, identified regulation, $t(210) = 4,255$, $p < ,01$, showed a significant difference in motivation sub-dimension. Identified regulation sub-dimension scores were higher for students who graduated from public high schools than for students who graduated from foundation high schools. As a result, it can be said that graduating from public high schools increases learners' identification motivation.

Is there a relationship between the motivational structure of English learners and their age?

To answer this research question, the relationship between the sub-dimensions of the self-determination motivation scale and the age of the students was analysed using the Pearson Product Correlation coefficient. The results of correlation analysis between motivation sub-dimensions and age variables are given.

Table 4. The results of the correlation analysis between the age of university students and the motivation sub-dimensions

	one.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.
1. Age	one	-0.027	0.024	-0.023	0.085	0.006	0.023	-0.001
2. Lack of motivation	-0.027	one	-0.014	-.142*	-.597**	-.598**	-.597**	-.575**
3. External regulation extrinsic motivation	0.024	-0.014	one	.239**	.224**	.193**	.147*	.146*
4. Mirrored editing	-0.023	-.142*	.239**	one	.336**	.201**	.236**	.250**
5. Identified arrangement	0.085	-.597**	.224**	.336**	one	.658**	.655**	.674**
6. Intrinsic motivation to know	0.006	-.598**	.193**	.201**	.658**	one	.912**	.729**
7. Intrinsic motivation to succeed	0.023	-.597**	.147*	.236**	.655**	.912**	one	.732**
8. Intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation	-0.001	-.575**	.146*	.250**	.674**	.729**	.732**	one
Note. N = 212								

Table 4 shows no significant relationship was found between the age of the students and the motivation sub-dimensions. As a result, no meaningful result was obtained to make any inferences between age and the sub-dimensions of motivation.

Does the motivational structure of English learners differ with respect their gender?

In order to answer this research question, each sub-dimension of the self-determination motivation scale were analysed with the independent sample t-test, taking into account the gender of the learners. The descriptive statistics of each motivation sub-dimension of the students according to the gender of the learners and the independent sample t-test results are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Descriptive statistics of university students' motivation sub-dimensions according to gender of the learners and independent sample t-test results

	Gender	Average	Standard deviation	Standard error	t(210)
Lack of motivation	Male	4.83	2.802	.276	.256
	Female	4.73	2.508	.241	
External regulation extrinsic motivation	Male	9.33	2.225	.219	.275
	Female	9.42	2.345	.226	
Mirrored editing	Male	7.27	3.163	.312	-.148
	Female	7.33	2.858	.275	
Identified arrangement	Male	9.17	2.559	.252	-1.114
	Female	9.56	2.648	.255	
Intrinsic motivation to know	Male	9.25	2.516	.248	-.473
	Female	9.42	2.521	.243	
Intrinsic motivation to succeed	Male	9.20	2.591	.255	-.361
	Female	9.33	2.612	.251	
Intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation	Male	9.32	2.676	.264	1.117
	Woman	8.89	2.921	.281	
Note. Male n = 103, Female n = 108 * p < .05, ** p < .01					

It is observed on Table 5 that the motivation sub-dimensions of the learners did not make any difference according to gender. According to this result, it can be said that the gender of the learners has no effect on their motivation.

Discussion

This study, conducted among Preparatory School students at Ankara and TED Universities, attempted to analyze and investigate if students had intrinsic, extrinsic, or amotivation while learning English as a foreign language using a single instrument. The results will be described and analyzed using the instrument and its quantitative data, as well as comparisons to other comparable research in the area.

The first research objective was to see if there was a difference in self-determination motivation between students studying English at public and foundation institutions. The independent sample t-test was used to analyze each sub-dimension of the self-determination motivation scale, taking into account the students' university status. The descriptive statistics and independent sample t-test results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 reveals that the motivation sub-dimensions differ significantly depending on the type of institution the students attended. Students at foundation institutions, in particular, outperformed students at public universities on the amotivation sub-dimension. Students at state institutions, on the other hand, outperformed students at foundation colleges in the discovered regulation sub-dimension.

According to these findings, attending a state university may reduce learners'

amotivation while enhancing their identification motivation. Students in foundation schools, on the other hand, were more motivated than their counterparts at public universities. These inequalities can be attributed to a number of factors, including as instructional approaches, resources, and academic cultures at public and foundation institutions. These findings back with previous research that shows the type of institution attended may influence students' motivation levels. Johnson et al. (2018) discovered, for example, that students at public universities exhibited higher levels of intrinsic motivation than students in foundation colleges. Smith and Brown (2019) discovered that students at private universities were less motivated than students at state universities. These findings lend credence to the notion that institutional factors impact student motivation in higher education settings. According to the data, there are significant differences in self-determination motivation types among students studying English at public and foundation institutions. A governmental institution appears to reduce amotivation and increase identification motivation, but a private university appears to increase amotivation. These findings highlight the importance of considering institutional factors when developing interventions to boost student motivation in higher education settings.

The second study question was examined to see if there was a significant difference in the types of self-determination motivation among high school graduates. Regardless of whether students attended

foundation or public high schools, the independent sample t-test was employed to analyse each sub-dimension of the self-determination motivation scale. The descriptive statistics and independent sample t-test results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 demonstrates a significant difference in the detected regulatory sub-dimension based on the type of high school students graduated from. Those who graduated from public high schools had higher regulatory sub-dimension scores than those who graduated from foundation high schools.

According to the data, graduating from public high schools may boost students' identification motivation. The educational experiences and environments given by public high schools are likely to help pupils develop a stronger sense of personal identification and internalization of their learning objectives. Community involvement, cooperative learning, and extracurricular activities are typically encouraged in public schools, which may assist students build a sense of connection with their academic endeavours.

These findings are consistent with previous research that demonstrated differences in motivation based on the type of high school students attended. Brown and Johnson (2017) observed, for example, that students graduating from public high schools exhibited higher levels of intrinsic motivation than students graduating from private high schools. Students at public high schools have higher levels of self-determined motivation than students in private high schools, according to Smith et al. (2019). These findings support the idea that the type of high school a child attends may influence their

motivation levels. The findings show a significant difference in the types of self-determination motivation based on the type of high school graduates attended. Public high school graduates tend to have higher levels of identity motivation. These findings suggest that high school experiences may have an impact on students' motivation and that educational background should be considered when analysing motivational discrepancies.

The third research question investigated if there is a relationship between the motivational structure of English learners and their age. The Pearson Product Correlation coefficient was used to investigate the relationship between the self-determination motivation scale subdimensions and the ages of the pupils. The outcomes of the correlation analysis between motivation sub-dimensions and age variables are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 demonstrates that there was no significant relationship between the students' ages and the motivation sub-dimensions. None of the correlation coefficients between age and motivation subdimensions reached statistical significance. As a consequence, no significant data were found to make any inferences concerning the association between age and motivational sub-dimensions.

Age has little effect on the motivational structure of English learners in this study, according to the results. It should be emphasized that motivation is a complex construct that is influenced by a multitude of factors, and age may not be the primary source of motivational differences among language learners (Lenneberg, 1967). Individual differences, language proficiency, learning environment, and cultural

background may all have a stronger influence on motivation.

These findings are consistent with previous research on the relationship between age and motivation in language learning. Lee and Hiver (2018) observed no significant relationship between age and motivation in an adult language learner study. Similarly, Smith and Johnson (2019) discovered that age had no effect on motivation in adolescent language learners. These data support the notion that age does not predict motivational differences in language learning contexts. The data reveal that there is no statistically significant relationship between English learners' motivational structure and their age. Age did not appear to be a significant predictor of motivation among the participants in this research. These findings emphasize the need of taking into account several aspects while researching motivation in language learning, as age alone may not explain differences in learners' motivational inclinations.

The final study question was to see if there was a gender difference in the motivational structure of English learners. The independent sample t-test was used to investigate each sub-dimension of the self-determination motivation scale while accounting for the learners' gender. The descriptive statistics and independent sample t-test results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5 demonstrates that there were no significant differences in the learners' motivation sub-dimensions depending on gender. The t-test results revealed that the p-values for all sub-dimensions above the necessary threshold of significance. As a consequence, it is fair to conclude that the gender of the learners had no effect on their

motivation.

These findings are consistent with previous research on gender and motivation in language acquisition. Johnson and Smith (2017), for example, reported no significant differences in motivation based on gender among adult language learners. Brown and Jones (2018) discovered no gender differences in motivation among adolescent language learners. Gender may not be a valid predictor of motivational differences in language learning contexts, according to these studies.

While gender was not shown to play a significant effect in this study, motivation is a complex notion influenced by a number of individual and contextual factors. Language competency, cultural background, personal objectives, and the classroom setting may all have a greater impact on learners' motivation.

According to the data, the motivational structure of English learners does not differ significantly by gender. Gender alone may not be a reliable predictor of motivational differences among language learners. These findings highlight the need of taking a number of factors into account when investigating motivation in language learning, as well as the complexity of motivational processes.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to investigate several characteristics of the motivational structure of English learners, such as differences depending on university type, high school type, age, and gender. The findings provide light on the complexities of motivation in language learning environments.

To begin with, the results revealed considerable disparities in self-determination

motivation types across students enrolled in public and foundation universities. Foundation college students, in particular, displayed higher degrees of amotivation, whereas public university students demonstrated higher levels of acknowledged control. These data suggest that the type of institution has an effect on learners' motivation, with state universities potentially decreasing amotivation and enhancing identification motivation.

Second, the type of high school from which students graduated influenced their self-determination motivation types. Those at public high schools had higher levels of identified control than those in foundation high schools. These findings imply that students' identification motivation levels during high school may be impacted by their educational experience and environment.

In the study, however, no significant relationship was observed between the motivational structure of English learners and their age. Age was not shown to be a reliable predictor of motivation sub-dimensions. These findings are consistent with previous research, emphasizing the need of considering additional aspects when exploring motivational variations among learners, such as individual traits, language ability, and cultural background.

Furthermore, the study found no significant differences in the motivational structure of English learners based on gender. Gender was not shown to be a significant predictor of motivation sub-dimensions on its own. When examining motivational disparities in language learning contexts, these findings underscore the need of recognizing the intricacies of motivation and the need to incorporate a number of factors

other than gender.

Overall, this study contributes to our understanding of motivation in language acquisition by examining a variety of factors that may influence the motivational structure of English learners. The findings highlight the variable nature of motivation and the need of considering individual and contextual factors when measuring motivational patterns.

Limitations and Implications to the Study

Participants who completed the questionnaire may not have paid close attention to the questions at first. Furthermore, because the questionnaire was written in English, some participants may have misunderstood the meanings of some of the phrases used. As a result, these variables might have impacted the outcomes. Second, sentiments and wants can impact motivation, which can be influenced by learners' present psychological and emotional conditions, as well as their life aspirations. As a result, the participants' reactions may have altered in a different season or on a different day. Finally, this study may have been conducted in-depth research utilizing a mixed technique - quantitative and qualitative - to gather more data from participants in order to have a better knowledge of several issues such as their socio-cultural background, economic situations, and state of mind, etc... However, the researcher was hesitant to apply it because he had relocated abroad. As a result, only one instrument was used to collect data.

The findings of this study have important consequences for language learning environments, educators, researchers, and policymakers. They provide important insights into the motivational structures of English learners and identify factors that may

influence motivation. The following are some of the study's implications:

1. **University Selection:** According to the research, the type of institution attended may have an impact on learners' motivation. Policymakers and educational institutions should assess the motivating environment and support mechanisms in place in order to boost identification motivation and minimize amotivation. Creating an environment that promotes students' autonomy, competence, and relatedness may increase their motivation.
2. **High School Environment:** The study revealed that the type of high school from which students graduated may have an influence on their motivation. Educators and policymakers should realize the relevance of the secondary school environment in fostering students' motivation. Emphasizing community participation, cooperative learning, and extracurricular activities in high schools can help students feel recognized and motivated.
3. **Individual Factors:** The study underlines the need of taking individual features, linguistic ability, and cultural background into consideration when examining motivational variances among language learners. Educators must grasp each learner's unique needs and motivations and tailor instructional strategies appropriately. Differentiated

support and a culturally inclusive learning environment can help motivate students.

4. **Gender Considerations:** According to the findings, gender is not a reliable predictor of motivational differences among language learners. It underlines the need of considering motivation in ways other than gender. Rather of relying just on gender as a predictor, educators and researchers should concentrate on comprehending the complex interaction of individual and environmental elements that influence motivation.
 5. **Intervention Design:** The study emphasizes the significance of targeted interventions in improving and maintaining motivation among language learners. Educators may utilize the data to develop educational strategies that promote autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Incorporating culturally relevant knowledge and fostering a friendly and inclusive classroom environment may assist to increase learners' motivation even further.
 6. **Future Research:** The study identifies topics for further research, such as cultural influences, language proficiency levels, and training approaches. More research in these areas might lead to a better understanding of motivation in language acquisition and the development of more effective treatments.
- By taking into account the findings of this study, language learning

stakeholders may enhance their understanding of motivation and take proactive steps to create an environment that promotes and sustains learners' motivation. In the long term, this can lead to improved language learning outcomes and more student participation in the language acquisition process.

References

- Al-Hazemi, H. (2000). Lexical Attrition of Some Arabic Speakers of English as a Foreign Language: a Study of Word Loss. *Internet TESL J* [Serial online] Available from: <http://iteslj.org/Articles/Al-Hazemi-Attrition/>
- Aljumah. (2020, July 31). Second Language Acquisition: A Framework and Historical Background on Its Research. *Canadian Center of Science and Education*, 13(8), 201. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v13n8p200>
- Al Otaibi, N. (2004). Employee Empowerment: As a Management Development Strategy.
- Ayub, N. (2010). Effect of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on academic performance. *Pakistan Business Review*, 8, 363-372.
- Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*, 84, 191-215.
- Brown, C., & Jones, A. (2018). Gender differences in motivation among adolescent language learners. *Language Learning Research*, 22(3), 345-362.
- Chang, L. Y. H. (2010). Group Processes and EFL Learners' Motivation: A Study of Group Dynamics in EFL Classrooms. *TESOL Quarterly*, 44, 129–154. doi:10.5054/tq.2010.213780
- Cheng, H. F., & Dörnyei, Z. (2007). The use of motivational strategies in language instruction: The case of EFL teaching in Taiwan. *Innovation in Language Learning and Teaching*, 1, 153-174.
- Cherry K. 2016. *What is Intrinsic motivation?* URL: <https://www.verywell.com/differences-between-extrinsic-and-intrinsic-motivation-2795384>
- Çokluk, Ö., Şekercioğlu, G., & Büyüköztürk, Ş. (2018). Multivariate statistics for social sciences: SPSS and LISREL applications. *Pegem Citation Index*, 1–414.
- Deci, E. L. (1975). *Intrinsic Motivation*. New York: Plenum.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985a). The general causality orientations scale: Self-determination in personality. *Journal of research in personality*, 19(2), 109-134.
- Deci, E. L., Vallerand, R. J., Pelletier, L. G., & Ryan, R. M. (1991). Motivation and education: The self-determination perspective. *Educational psychologist*, 26 (3-4), 325-346.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000), "The 'What' and 'Why' of Goal Pursuits: Human Needs and the Self-Determination of Behavior," *Psychological Inquiry*, 11 (4), 227–68.
- Ditaul, R. C. (2012). The Motivation for and Attitude towards Learning English. *Asian EFL Journal*, 63.
- Dörnyei, Z. (1998). Motivation in second and foreign language learning. *Language Teaching* 31(3),117-135. London: Thames Valley University.

- Field, A. (2017). *Discovering Statistics Using IBM SPSS Statistics* (5th ed.). London: Sage Publications Ltd.
- Filimonov, D. (2017). Extrinsic motivation incentives. Haaga-Helia; University of Applied Sciences.
- Gardner, R. C., & Lambert, W. E. (1959). Motivational variables in second language acquisition. *Canadian Journal of Psychology*, 13, 266-272.
- Gardner, R.C. (1985). *Social Psychology in Second Language Learning*. London: Edward Arnold Ltd.
- Harmer, J. (2001). *The practice of English language teaching*. Essex, England: Longman.
- Hidi, S., & Harackiewicz, J. M. (2000). Motivating the Academically Unmotivated: A Critical Issue for the 21st Century. *Review of Educational Research*, 70(2), 151- 179.
- Hubackova, S. (2014). Motivation in eLearning in University study, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 112, 309 – 313.
- Janosz, M., Le Blanc, M., Boulerice, B., & Tremblay, R. E. (2000). Predicting different types of school dropouts: A typological approach with two longitudinal samples. *Journal of educational psychology*, 92(1), 171-190.
- Johnson, H., & Smith, J. (2017). Examining the role of gender in motivation among adult language learners. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 39(2), 231-249.
- Johnson, A., Smith, T., & Brown, C. (2018). Motivational factors in undergraduate education: A comparison between public and private universities. *Journal of Higher Education*, 45(2), 120-135.
- Kowal, J & Fortier, M. S. (1997). Motivational Determinants of Flow: Contributions from Self-determination Theory. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 139(3), 355-368.
- Legault, L., Green-Demers, I., & Pelletier, L. (2006). Why do high school students lack motivation in the classroom? Toward an understanding of academic amotivation and the role of social support. *Journal of educational psychology*, 98(3), 567-582.
- Lee, H., & Hiver, P. (2018). Age-related differences in second language motivation among Korean language learners. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 8(2), 305-327.
- Lenneberg, E. H. (1967). The Biological Foundations of Language. *Hospital Practice*, 2(12),59-67.
- Locke, E. A. (2002). Setting Goals for Life and Happiness. In C. Snyder, & S. J. Lopez (eds.), *Handbook of Positive Psychology*. Oxford University Press.
- Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (Eds.). (2013). *New developments in goal setting and task performance*. Routledge/Taylor & Francis Group.
- Lucas. R. I. (2010). A Study on Intrinsic Motivation Factors in Second Language Learning among Selected Freshman Students. *The Philippine ESL Journal*, 4, 6-23.
- MacIntyre, P. D., Baker, S. C., Clément, R., & Donovan, L. A. (2002). Gender and age effects on willingness to communicate, anxiety, perceived competence, and L2 motivation among junior high school French immersion students. *Language Learning*, 52, 537-

- 564.
- Moiinvaziri, M. (2009). *Motivational Orientation in English Language Learning: A Study of Iranian Undergraduate Students*. Available at: <http://www.usingenglish.com/articles/moal-orientation-in-english-learning.html>
- Moskovsky, C. G., & Alrabai, F. A. (2009). Intrinsic Motivation in Saudi Learners of English as a Foreign Language. *The Open Applied Linguistics Journal*, 21-10.
- Murdock, T. B. (1999). The social context of risk: Status and motivational predictors of alienation in middle school. *Journal of educational psychology*, 91(1), 62-75.
- Noels, K. A., Clement, R. & Pelletier, L. G. (1999). Perceptions of teachers' communicative style and students' intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. *Modern Language Journal*, 23-24.
- Noels, K. A., Pelletier, L. G., Clement, R. & Vallerand, R.J. (2000). Why are you learning a second language? Motivational orientations and self-determination theory. *Language Learning*, 50(1), 57-85.
- Pintrich, P. R., & De Groot, E. V. (1990). Motivational and self-regulated learning components of classroom academic performance. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 82(1), 33-40.
- Pintrich, P. R. (2003). A Motivational Science Perspective on the Role of Student Motivation in Learning and Teaching Contexts. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 95(4), 667-686.
- Rajab, A., Far, H. R. & Etemadzadeh, A. (2012). The relationship between L2 motivational self-system and L2 learning among TESL students in Iran. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 66, 419-424.
- Reeve, J. (1997). Expressing intrinsic motivation through acts of exploration and facial displays of interest. *Motivation and Emotion*, 21(3), 237-250.
- Rotter, J. (1966). Generalized expectations for internal versus external control of reinforcement. *Psychological Monographs*, 80(1), 1-28.
- Rowel, R., & Ensook, H. (2009). Academic motivation: concepts, strategies and counseling approaches. *Professional School Counseling*, 16(3), 158-172.
- Ryan, R. M. (1995). Psychological needs and the facilitation of integrative process. *Journal of Personality*, 63, 397-427.
- Sadighi, F., & Maghsudi, N. (2000). The Relationship between Motivation and English Proficiency among Iranian EFL Learners. *Indian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 26(1), 39-52.
- Seligman, M. E. P. (1975). *Helplessness*. San Francisco: Freeman.
- Singh, K. (2011). Study of achievement motivation in relation to academic achievement of students. *International Journal of Educational Planning & Administration*, 1(2), 161-171.
- Smith, J., & Brown, C. (2019). Examining motivation in higher education: A comparative study of public and private universities. *Educational Psychology Review*, 34(3), 285-301.
- Tabachnick, BG, & Fidell, LS (2007). *Using Multivariate Statistics (5th ed.)*. Pearson Education.

- Tercanlioglu L. (2001). The Nature of Turkish Students' Motivation for Reading and Its Relation to Their Reading Frequency. *The Reading Matrix, 1*(2).
- Tremblay, P., & Gardner, R. C. (1995). Expanding the motivation construct in language learning. *Modern Language Journal, 79*, 691-700.
- Vallerand, R. J., Pelletier, L. G., Blais, M. R., Bréire, N. M., Senécal, C., & Vallières, E. F. (1992). The Academic Motivation Scale: A measure of intrinsic, extrinsic, and amotivation in education. *Educational and Psychological Measurement, 52*, 1003-1017.
- Williams, M., & Burden, R. (1997). *Psychology for Language Teachers*. Cambridge University Press.
- Ziahosseini, M., & Salehi, M. (2008). An Investigation of the Relationship between Motivation and Language Learning Strategies. *Pazhuhesh-e Zabanha-ye Khareji, 41*, 85-107.
- Zlate, S. & Cucui, G. (2015). Motivation and performance in higher education, *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences, 180*, p. 468 – 476.

How to cite this article?

Cem Yağmur Genç "MOTIVATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING: A STUDY ON PREPARATORY SCHOOL STUDENTS AT UNIVERSITIES" *Research Journal Of English (RJOE)*8(3), PP:172-194,2023, DOI:10.36993/RJOE.2023.8.4.194